

Definition

A set $E \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ is **Lebesgue measurable** if for every $\epsilon > 0$, there is an open set G so that $E \subseteq G$ and

$$m^*(G \setminus E) < \epsilon.$$

In this case, we define the **Lebesgue measure** of E , denoted by $m(E)$, to be

$$m(E) = m^*(E).$$

Examples of Lebesgue Measurable Sets

Many sets are Lebesgue measurable, including:

- 1 any set of measure 0 (such as discrete sets like $\{5, 9, 12, 13\}$ or \mathbb{Q})
- 2 open intervals and closed intervals
- 3 union or intersection of a countable collection of open sets, such as the interval $(0, 1]$ which is equal to $\bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(0, 1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)$
- 4 union or intersection of a countable collection of closed sets, such as the set \mathbb{Q} which is a countable union of rational numbers r_1, r_2, r_3, \dots (because we know that \mathbb{Q} is countable).

There exist sets that are non-Lebesgue measurable, but we skip the details here.

Definition

Let f be defined on $I = [a, b]$. We say that f is **Lebesgue measurable on I** if for every $s \in \mathbb{R}$, the set

$$\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$$

is a Lebesgue measurable set.

Let us first turn our attention to the set $\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$. We have to understand what this set means, before we can discuss examples.

Understanding $\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$

Let $f(x) = 2x - 5$ on $I = [-1, 3]$. Fill up the table on the next slide.

Understanding $\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$

Let $f(x) = 2x - 5$ on $I = [-1, 3]$.

s	$\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$
-10	
-6	
-5	
-3	
1	
2	

Answers

Let $f(x) = 2x - 5$ on $I = [-1, 3]$.

s	$\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$
-10	$[-1, 3]$
-6	$(-\frac{1}{2}, 3]$
-5	$(0, 3]$
-3	$(1, 3]$
1	\emptyset
2	\emptyset

Understanding $\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$

Let $f(x) = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x$ on $I = [-6, 9]$. Fill up the table on the next slide.

Understanding $\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$

Let $f(x) = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x$ on $I = [-6, 9]$.

s	$\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$
-1	
0	
1	
2	
3	
4	
5	

Answers

Let $f(x) = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x$ on $I = [-6, 9]$.

s	$\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$
-1	$[-6, 9)$
0	$[-6, 6)$
1	$[-6, 3)$
2	$[-6, 0)$
3	$[-6, -3)$
4	\emptyset
5	\emptyset

Understanding $\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$

Let $f(x) = x^2 - 2$ on $I = [-2, 3]$. Fill up the table on the next slide.

Understanding $\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$

Let $f(x) = x^2 - 2$ on $I = [-2, 3]$.

s	$\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$
-3	
-2	
-1	
0	
1	
2	
3	
4	

Answers

Let $f(x) = x^2 - 2$ on $I = [-2, 3]$.

s	$\{x \in I \mid f(x) > s\}$
-3	$[-2, 3]$
-2	$[-2, 0) \cup (0, 3]$
-1	$[-2, -1) \cup (1, 3]$
0	$[-2, -\sqrt{2}) \cup (\sqrt{2}, 3]$
1	$[-2, -\sqrt{3}) \cup (\sqrt{3}, 3]$
2	$(2, 3]$
3	$(\sqrt{5}, 3]$
4	$(\sqrt{6}, 3]$

Is $y = 2x - 5$ a measurable function on $[-1, 3]$?

Return to the definition of a Lebesgue measurable function. We want to check if the set $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = 2x - 5 > s\}$ is a measurable set for all $s \in \mathbb{R}$.

Fill up the following table. *Graph available in previous slide.*

If ...	Then $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = 2x - 5 > s\} =$
$s < -7$	
$s = -7$	
$-7 < s < 1$	
$s = 1$	
$s > 1$	

Is $y = 2x - 5$ a measurable function on $[-1, 3]$?

Return to the definition of a Lebesgue measurable function. We want to check if the set $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = 2x - 5 > s\}$ is a measurable set for all $s \in \mathbb{R}$.

Fill up the following table. *Graph available in previous slide.*

Answers:

If ...	Then $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = 2x - 5 > s\} =$
$s < -7$	$[-1, 3]$
$s = -7$	$(-1, 3]$
$-7 < s < 1$	$(s, 3]$
$s = 1$	\emptyset
$s > 1$	\emptyset

Note: Since all the sets on the second column are measurable sets, then $y = 2x - 5$ is a measurable function on $[-1, 3]$.

Is $y = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x$ a measurable function on $[-6, 9]$?

Return to the definition of a Lebesgue measurable function. We want to check if the set $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x > s\}$ is a measurable set for all $s \in \mathbb{R}$.

Fill up the following table. *Graph available in previous slide.*

Answers:

If ...	Then $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x > s\} =$
$s < -1$	
$s = -1$	
$-1 < s < 4$	
$s = 4$	
$s \geq 4$	

Is $y = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x$ a measurable function on $[-6, 9]$?

Return to the definition of a Lebesgue measurable function. We want to check if the set $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x > s\}$ is a measurable set for all $s \in \mathbb{R}$.

Fill up the following table. *Graph available in previous slide.*

Answers:

If ...	Then $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x > s\} =$
$s < -1$	$[-6, 9]$
$s = -1$	$(-6, 9]$
$-1 < s < 4$	$[-6, s)$
$s = 4$	\emptyset
$s \geq 4$	\emptyset

Note: Since all the sets on the second column are measurable sets, then $y = 2 - \frac{1}{3}x$ is a measurable function on $[-6, 9]$.

Is $y = x^2 - 2$ a measurable function on $[-2, 3]$?

Return to the definition of a Lebesgue measurable function. We want to check if the set $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = x^2 - 2 > s\}$ is a measurable set for all $s \in \mathbb{R}$.

Fill up the following table. *Graph available in previous slide.*

If ...	Then $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = x^2 - 2 > s\} =$
$s < -2$	
$s = -2$	
$-2 < s < 2$	
$s = 2$	
$2 < s < 7$	
$s = 7$	
$s > 7$	

Note: Since all the sets on the second column are measurable sets, then $y = x^2 - 2$ is a measurable function on $[-2, 3]$.

Is $y = x^2 - 2$ a measurable function on $[-2, 3]$?

Return to the definition of a Lebesgue measurable function. We want to check if the set $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = x^2 - 2 > s\}$ is a measurable set for all $s \in \mathbb{R}$.

Fill up the following table. *Graph available in previous slide.*

Answers:

If ...	Then $\{x \in I \mid f(x) = x^2 - 2 > s\} =$
$s < -2$	$[-2, 3]$
$s = -2$	$[-2, 0) \cup (0, 3]$
$-2 < s < 2$	$[-2, -\sqrt{s+2}) \cup (\sqrt{s+2}, 3]$
$s = 2$	$[-2, -2) \cup (2, 3]$
$2 < s < 7$	$(\sqrt{s+2}, 3]$
$s = 7$	\emptyset
$s > 7$	\emptyset

Note: Since all the sets on the second column are measurable sets, then $y = x^2 - 2$ is a measurable function on $[-2, 3]$.

Definition

The **characteristic function** of A , denoted by χ_A , is the function defined by

$$\chi_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Exercise: If $A = [0, 1] \cup 5 \cup (10, 12]$, sketch the graph of $\chi_A(x)$.

Characteristic Function

Answer Key:

Is χ_A a measurable function?

To determine whether χ_A is a measurable function on $[-1, 13]$, where $A = [0, 1] \cup 5 \cup (10, 12]$, we again fill up the table like in the previous slide.

Fill up this table:

If ...	Then $\{x \in I \mid \chi_A(x) > s\} =$
$s < 0$	
$s = 0$	
$0 < s < 1$	
$s = 1$	
$s > 1$	

Is χ_A a measurable function?

Answer Key:

If ...	Then $\{x \in I \mid \chi_A(x) > s\} =$
$s < 0$	$[-1, 13]$
$s = 0$	A
$0 < s < 1$	A
$s = 1$	\emptyset
$s > 1$	\emptyset

Note: $[-1, 13]$ and \emptyset are measurable sets. The set A is a union of measurable sets, and so must be measurable (see Slide no. 2). Therefore, because all sets in the second column are measurable, then the *function* χ_A is measurable.

Observe also that $\chi_A(x)$ is measurable if and only if A is measurable. If A above is not measurable, then there would be one set in the second column that is not measurable, so the *function* χ_A would also be not measurable.

Definition

A **simple function** is a function ϕ defined on the interval I of the form

$$\phi(x) = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \chi_{E_k}(x),$$

where a_k are constants and $\{E_k\}$ are pairwise disjoint measurable sets.

Exercise 1: Prove that χ_A in the previous slide is simple.

Exercise 2: Prove that $f(x) = \begin{cases} 7 & \text{if } x \leq 3 \\ 8 & \text{if } x > 5 \\ -6 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$ defined on $[2, 10]$ is a simple function.

Answer Key:

(1.) χ_A in the previous slide is simple because it can be expressed as

$$\phi(x) = 1\chi_A(x) + 0\chi_{A^c}(x).$$

(2.) f is a simple function because it can be expressed as

$$f(x) = 7\chi_{[2,3]}(x) - 6\chi_{(3,5]}(x) + 8\chi_{(5,10]}.$$

Definition

Let $\phi(x) = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \chi_{E_k}(x)$ be a simple function on the interval I . The **Lebesgue integral** of ϕ on I is defined to be

$$(L) \int_I \phi = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k m(E_k).$$

Exercise 1: Compute the Lebesgue integral of

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 7 & \text{if } x \leq 3 \\ 8 & \text{if } x > 5 \\ -6 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \text{on } [2, 10].$$

Exercise 2: Compute the Lebesgue integral of $g(x) = \begin{cases} 3 & \text{if } x \in \mathbb{Q} \\ -2 & \text{if } x \notin \mathbb{Q} \end{cases}$ on $[0, 15]$.

Answer Key (1):

(1.) Let $E_1 = [2, 3]$, $E_2 = (3, 5]$, and $E_3 = (5, 10]$.

Their measures on $I = [2, 10]$ are: $m(E_1) = 1$, $m(E_2) = 2$, and $m(E_3) = 5$.
Note that the total is 8, which is the measure of $[2, 10]$.

Recall that $f(x) = 7\chi_{[2,3]}(x) - 6\chi_{(3,5]}(x) + 8\chi_{(5,10]}(x)$.

$$\Rightarrow (L) \int_{[2,10]} f = 7(1) - 6(2) + 8(5) = 35.$$

Answer Key (2):

(1.) Let $E_1 = \mathbb{Q}$ and $E_2 = \mathbb{Q}^c$.

Their measures on $I = [0, 15]$ are: $m(E_1) = 0$ and $m(E_2) = 15$. *Note that the total is 15, which is the measure of $[0, 15]$.*

$$\Rightarrow (L) \int_{[0,15]} g = 3(0) - 2(15) = -30.$$

Note: The function g is an example of a function that is NOT Riemann integrable on $[0, 15]$ but is Lebesgue integrable on $[0, 15]$.